

SPIRITUALITY AND CULTURE, THEIR RELATIONSHIP

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Annotations: The article studies the language as the embodiment of the entire spectrum of the spiritual life of society. The author substantiates that language is a universal spiritual reflection of reality, it corresponds to the structure of society, stimulates the development of national life, forms cultures.

Keywords: language, spiritual culture, society, personality, spirituality.

The contradictory process of the development of social relations, the growth of the role of the subjects of these relations, the person, the individual makes it necessary to search for optimal ways of functioning, enriching the spiritual life of society. The socio-philosophical study of this problem is of particular importance in our time. The objective reasons, which actualizes the importance of the problems of the spiritual life of society and linguistic culture, are the comprehensive revival of culture, spirituality, and their convergence with universal problems based on the growing integration of peoples' lives. The study of language as a spiritual phenomenon that reflects the whole complex of human existence, the historical and cultural development of society is reflected.

In our opinion, the main task facing modern society in the sphere of spiritual life is to create conditions for the most complete development of the multifaceted potential of spirituality and culture by a person. It is also extremely important to create conditions for the comprehensive self-realization of the spiritual and cultural potential, the essential forces of a person, one's spiritual worldview, and worldview. It is important to emphasize that the spiritual life of society is an extremely broad concept that includes multifaceted processes, phenomena associated with the spiritual sphere of people's life; a set of views, ideas, ideas, language, feelings of people, the process of their production, distribution, the transformation of social, individual ideas into the inner world of a person. The spiritual life of society embraces the ideal world (a set of ideas, views, hypotheses, theories) together with its bearers — social subjects — individuals, peoples, ethnic groups. In this regard, it is appropriate to talk about the personal spiritual life of an individual, his spiritual world, about the spiritual life of a particular social subject - a people, an ethnic group, about the spiritual life of society as a whole. The basis of spiritual life is the spiritual world of a person - his spiritual values, worldview orientations. At the same time, in the spiritual world of an individual, individuality is impossible outside the spiritual life of society. Therefore, spiritual life is always a dialectical unity of the individual and the social, which functions as an individual-social.

In modern conditions of spiritual development, the role and significance of the formation of moral values in the public consciousness, which significantly activates the processes of moral regulation of social relations, the cultural and moral development of a person, speech culture, and the progress of society as a whole, are becoming more and more relevant. At the same time, the versatility of the values of spiritual life, a particular individual, a team significantly expands the scope of application of moral principles in all spheres of society,

contributing to the formation of high social and moral qualities of people. Therefore, it is so important in modern conditions that spiritual values become an integral feature of a person's spiritual life, his moral character, serve as an assessment criterion and regulator of a person's behavior, his moral maturity. In all spheres of the spirituality of the society of consciousness and moral relations, language culture and moral practice, feelings, the formation of values and ideals, the role and importance of spiritual principles and norms are growing more and more. Spiritual culture as an element of spiritual life, social, spiritual relations includes a certain system of values, knowledge, language, beliefs, worldview orientations, norms, traditions in organic unity with the social humanistically significant activity of people in the development, creation of being. Spiritual culture is created by the activity of social subjects and is aimed at transforming social life, developing the essential forces of a person, in particular his spirituality, their comprehensive self-realization; it is not only consciousness but also a social activity that transforms the activity of the individual, which is measured by the amount of spiritual, socio-humanistic values it creates. Such a culture testifies to the ability of each individual to perceive the advanced, progressive in social life, as well as to spread it, create it by the creative forces and abilities of each individual; about the readiness of the individual for self-giving, self-development of one's spirituality, both for the sake of the individual and for the sake of the whole society. The values of a spiritual culture are a dialectical unity of the national and universal. It is impossible both without the values of a specific national culture and without the national values developed by mankind. The value content of spiritual culture can act as a driving force for social progress only when the creative potential of such a culture is based on a common system of values developed by mankind throughout its history. In this regard, it should be mentioned that certain social functions of spiritual culture are distinguished in literature. Among the main such functions are cognitive, communicative, regulatory, prognostic, value-oriented, which are organically interconnected. But, according to many philosophers, culturologists, the integrating function of spiritual culture is a human-creative function. At the same time, it can be said that the measure of the development of spiritual culture is determined by the measure of the development of the essential values of a person, the versatility and versatility of the forms of self-realization of his spiritual potential, individual self-affirmation. Increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of the process of forming a spiritual culture involves creating conditions for the self-realization of the wealth of human spirituality because the main content of the values of such culture lies in their self-expression and reproduction. The development of spiritual culture is impossible without the approval of its values, in particular at the personal level, which makes it possible to realize the potential of the uniqueness, originality of the individual, his spirituality, the importance of which in the progress of social life is constantly growing.

It seems to us that the culture and art of communication is not an end in itself, but a precious asset of a person. This is a means of spiritual development and improvement of a person who strives for a sense of self-worth. The acquisition by a person of the skills of a culture of communication will solve many problems of interpersonal, international relations, as well as society as a whole. Moreover, language is the best means of mutual relations between individuals, a means of their spiritual unification and mutual influence. Without a language, there is no nationality, the native language best reflects the thoughts and feelings of an individual, society, and the whole people. The language, its history, development, and

elaboration reflect the first signs of the manifestation of the independent spiritual life of a separate society. The main individual features of a society are its language, literature, art, songs, and oral art. Summing up, we can conclude that the spiritual life of society is an extremely important element of its life, on the optimal development process of which its overall progress depends. The main direct subject of the spiritual life of society, in particular spiritual culture, is a person, a person. The whole system of purposeful activity of social subjects should be aimed at creating comprehensive conditions for self-realization of a person's spiritual potential, language culture, creative self-realization of his essential forces, various life manifestations, and the development of new spiritual guidelines. Today, culture and language are united in the field of spiritual values of each person and the whole society. Perhaps no one will deny that in the culture of the language there are clear signs of the spirituality of the individual and society.

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